

Role of Ultrasonography Parameters to Characterise Benign vS Malignant Focal Hepatic Lesions in Correlation with Triple Phase Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography and / or Histopathological Findings

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Abstract:

Objectives: The present study was to evaluate the role of ultrasonography parameters to characterise focal liver lesions. And to assess the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasonography in the evaluation of focal liver lesions in correlation with Triple phase CECT and/or histopathological examination.

Methods: Patients meeting the specified criteria underwent a thorough ultrasound examination of liver that was carried out with GE Voluson S10, GE Voluson S6, using 1-5 MHz curvilinear probe and 12 MHz linear probe. The patients were followed up with Triple phase CECT abdomen and/or histopathological examination. **Results:** The mean age of study participants was 51.8 ± 15.6 years. Majority of patients belonged to 41-50 and 51-60 years of age group. There was a higher prevalence of focal liver lesions in males (70%) compared to females (30%). In USG examination, normal size of liver was seen in 48% of patients while hepatomegaly was seen in 47% of patients. Multifocal lesions (54%) were more commonly observed than single lesion (46%). Hypochoic pattern of echogenicity was the predominant finding on ultrasound, noted in 54.6% of cases. Of all the focal liver lesions, benign lesions were most commonly observed (52%) than malignant lesions (48%). **Conclusions:** USG with colour Doppler should be used as a first line screening modality due to its high diagnostic accuracy in the evaluation of focal liver lesions along with additional advantages like its non-invasiveness, widespread availability, cost effectiveness and lack of radiation exposure.

Key words: Focal Hepatic Lesions, Ultrasonography, Triple phase Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography, Histopathological findings

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Introduction

Focal hepatic lesions are common findings as a result of increasing use of imaging techniques in patients with nonspecific abdominal complaints. They may be infective or neoplastic (benign or malignant) in origin [1]

The blood supply to liver is unique due to its dual supply from both the hepatic artery and portal vein [1,2]. Typically, the portal vein supplies 70% of the liver's blood, but in most cases of primary and a few metastatic liver disorders, the hepatic artery

becomes the primary source of blood flow, which reverses the usual proportion of blood supply to the liver. ³ Triple phase contrast enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT) leverages the variation in blood flow to differentiate between benign and malignant lesions and precisely characterise them [2].

Liver imaging can be achieved through various methods, including plain radiographs, ultrasound,

CT scans, radioisotope studies, MRI, and invasive procedures such as angiography, percutaneous transhepatic cholangiography, and endoscopic retrograde cholangiography [3].

Ultrasonography (USG) stands out as a non-invasive, cost-effective method capable of detecting various abnormalities in the liver, gallbladder, and other organs. Additionally, it does not involve ionizing radiation [4,5]. It exhibits high sensitivity in identifying liver mass lesions and offers real-time assessment of the entire organ. However, its effectiveness is reliant on the operator's skill, necessitates expertise, relies on patient cooperation, and poses challenges in obese individuals [5].

Also, sonography can be used as an imaging guide for FNAC of these suspicious lesions and also in therapeutic drainage of abscesses that might obviate curative hepatic resection. USG-guided FNAC of the liver lesion is a safe, simple, cost-effective method for histopathological diagnosis of hepatic focal lesions with good sensitivity and specificity [6].

Ultrasonography is useful for the practitioner as a first imaging procedure in direct correlation to the clinical examination. It gives valuable information regarding parameters such as site, size, number of lesions, nature of lesions, relation to surrounding structures and vascularity [7,8].

Since USG is the primary screening modality, the parameters that aid in characterisation of focal hepatic lesions can be evaluated in correlation with Triple phase contrast enhanced computed tomography (CECT) and/or histopathological examination (HPE).

Aims & Objectives:

- To evaluate the role of ultrasonography parameters to characterise focal liver lesions.
- To assess the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasonography in the evaluation of focal liver lesions in correlation with Triple phase CECT and/or histopathological examination.

Materials and Methods

Source of Data

Patients referred for USG abdomen to the Department of Radio-diagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences are included in the study.

Sample Size

All the consecutive patients who satisfy the inclusion and exclusion criteria during the study period.

Type of Study

Prospective observational study.

Method of Collection of Data

Prospective consecutive sampling of the patients referred for ultrasound abdomen to the Department

of Radio diagnosis was done and confirmed by Triple phase contrast enhanced CT / histopathological examination. The period of study was from July 2022 – January 2024.

Patients meeting the specified criteria underwent a thorough ultrasound examination of liver that was carried out with GE Voluson S10, GE Voluson S6, using 1-5 MHz curvilinear probe and 12 MHz linear probe.

The liver was examined with real-time ultrasound following a 6-hour fasting period to minimize bowel gas interference. The examination was performed during suspended respiration to ensure thorough evaluation of dome of liver.

The following characteristics of the lesion were studied.

- The number and size of lesions.
- The segmental location of the lesion.
- Echogenicity of the lesion.
- Margins of the lesion.
- The presence of calcification/septa/central scar.
- Vascularity of the lesion on Colour Doppler flow imaging.

The patients were followed up with Triple phase CECT abdomen and/or histopathological examination.

The patients who underwent Triple phase CECT abdomen underwent a Non-Contrast CT (NCCT) of the abdomen followed by a contrast-enhanced CT (CECT). The contrast medium used was Iopromide, a non-ionic iodinated IV contrast agent, administered at a dose of 1.5 ml/kg body weight (with a maximum dose of 150 ml). It was injected using a Pressure Injector Medrad at a rate of 4 cc/sec through an 18G IV catheter.

Protocol for Triple Phase CECT Abdomen

- Contrast Medium - Iopromide (nonionic iodinated I.V contrast media).
- Rate of injection - Given with Pressure Injector Medrad at the rate of 4cc/sec.
- Volume of Contrast Material - Dose of 1.5ml/kg body weight (max dose: 150ml)
- Scanning Delays (sec) per each phase –

20 secs -arterial

50 secs-venous

90 secs-delayed

- Collimation(mm) - 5
- Reconstruction interval(mm) - 0.6
- Gantry rotation speed(sec)- 0.6
- Pitch -1.375:1
- Kilovolts -120
- Milliampere- 600
- Superior extent - dome of diaphragm

- Inferior extent -iliac crest.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all age groups with focal hepatic lesions who have undergone ultrasonography.
- All patients who have undergone True cut core biopsy/FNAC/Surgery and/or Triple phase CECT.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who have not undergone any one of the modalities like USG/CECT abdomen or without any histopathological examination.
- Already proven cases of hepatic tumours by CT scans or histopathology.

Observations and Results

Table 1: Distribution of Locality of Lesion in Liver:

Locality	Frequency	Percentages
Right Lobe	61	41
Left Lobe	20	13
Both Lobes	69	46

Table 2: Distribution of Cases Diagnosed by Histopathological Examination:

HPE diagnosis	Number	%
HCC	14	13.7 %
Fibrolamellar carcinoma	1	1.0 %
Hemangioma	3	2.9 %
Hepatoblastoma	1	1.0 %
Hepatic cyst	2	2.0 %
Cholangiocarcinoma	2	2.0 %
Biliary cystadenoma	1	1.0 %
Metastases	34	33.3 %
Hydatid cyst	9	8.8 %
Abscess	35	34.3 %

Table 3: Correlation of Usg Diagnosis of Various Focal Liver Lesions with Triple Phase CECT / HPE Findings:

USG Findings	Triple Phase CECT / HPE Findings										
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	Total
Metastases	47	4	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	54
Abscess	1	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	47
Fibrolamellar carcinoma	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
HCC	3	11	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	15
Hepatoblastoma	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Hemangioma	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	4
Cholangiocarcinoma	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
Biliary cystadenoma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Hydatid cyst	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	14
Hepatic cyst	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	10	11
Total	52	15	48	1	5	1	2	1	15	10	150

A- Metastases, B – HCC, C- Abscess, D- Fibrolamellar carcinoma, E- Hemangioma, F- Hepatoblastoma, G – Cholangiocarcinoma, H- Biliary cystadenoma, I – Hydatid cyst, J – Hepatic cyst

Table 4: USG Diagnosis of Focal Liver Lesions in Correlation with Triple Phase CECT / HPE Findings

	True positive	False positive	False negative	True negative	Total
HCC	11	4	4	131	150
Metastases	47	7	5	91	150
Abscess	45	2	2	101	150
Hydatid cyst	14	0	1	135	150
Hemangioma	3	1	0	146	150
Hepatoblastoma	1	0	0	149	150
Fibrolamellar carcinoma	1	0	0	149	150
Biliary cystadenoma	1	0	0	149	150
Cholangiocarcinoma	1	0	0	149	150
Hepatic cyst	10	1	0	139	150

Table 5: Diagnostic Accuracy of Usg in Diagnosis of Focal Liver Lesions with Triple Phase CECT / HPE Findings

	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy	p value
HCC	73.33%	97.04%	73.33%	97.04%	94.67%	<0.001
Metastases	90.38%	92.86%	87.04%	94.79%	92%	
Abscess	95.74%	98.06%	95.74%	98.06%	97.33%	
Hydatid cyst	93.30%	100%	100%	99.20%	99.30%	
Hemangioma	100%	99.32%	75%	100%	99.33%	
Hepatoblastoma	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Fibrolamellar carcinoma	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Biliary cystadenoma	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Cholangiocarcinoma	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Hepatic cyst	100%	99.29%	90.91%	100%	99.33%	

Table 6: Characterisation of Benign Vs Malignant Focal Liver Lesions by USG in Correlation with Triple Phase CECT / HPE

	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
Benign	94.94%	97.18%	97.40%	94.52%	96%
Malignant	97.18%	94.94%	94.52%	97.40%	96%

Findings

Table 7: Diagnostic Accuracy of USG in Lesion Characterisation in Correlation with Triple Phase CECT / HPE Findings

	True positive	False positive	False negative	True negative	Total
Benign	75	2	4	69	150
Malignant	69	4	2	75	150

Discussions

The present study was done on 150 Patients, referred to the radiology department for ultrasound examination (USG). Out of them only those who underwent Triple phase CECT/Histopathological examination in Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences were included.

The mean age of study participants was 51.8 ± 15.6 years. Majority of patients belonged to 41-50 and 51-60 years of age group. There was a higher prevalence of focal liver lesions in males (70%)

compared to females (30%). In USG examination, normal size of liver was seen in 48% of patients while hepatomegaly was seen in 47% of patients. Multifocal lesions (54%) were more commonly observed than single lesion (46%).

Hypochoic pattern of echogenicity was the predominant finding on ultrasound, noted in 54.6% of cases. Of all the focal liver lesions, benign lesions were most commonly observed (52%) than malignant lesions (48%).

Fig 4: CASE 1: Liver metastases from primary pancreatic adenocarcinoma. A - USG image shows multiple well-defined hyperechoic lesions with hypoechoic halo giving the characteristic Bull's eye pattern. B & C- Axial sections of venous phase in Triple phase CECT shows multiple hypoenhancing lesions in both lobes of liver. Hypoenhancing lesion also noted in tail of pancreas. D- FNAC showing features consistent with metastatic adenocarcinoma.

Metastases

This was the most common focal liver lesion encountered in our study. Among the 52 cases of metastases identified in our study, 31 cases (59.6%) were male and 21 cases (40.3%) were female. Metastases were more prevalent among males than females, and the majority of affected individuals were in the age group of 51-60 years, this was also observed by Griscom JT et al [9].

94.2% of the cases were multifocal in distribution. The most observed echogenicity pattern was hypoechoic which was seen in 30 cases (57.6%). This was also observed in previous studies by Jain AK et al [10]. Bull's eye pattern of lesion (hyperechoic lesion with hypoechoic halo) was seen in 9 cases (17.3%). 5 cases (9.6%) showed heterogeneous echogenicity and 7 lesions (13.4%) were hyperechoic. One case (1.9%) also showed anechoic pattern from primary carcinoma pancreas. Two cases of calcified metastases were also identified, originating from carcinoma colorectum.

Hypoechoic lesions indicating hypovascular metastases were most commonly seen from metastatic breast and lung. Conversely, hyperechoic lesions, due to hypervascular metastases were commonly seen from primary renal cell carcinoma, neuroendocrine tumour and gastrointestinal tumours. Calcified metastases were seen from primary mucinous adenocarcinoma colon. The findings in our study were comparable to the observation made by Withers C.E and Wilson S.R [11].

The most common primary lesion to metastasize to the liver was carcinoma colorectum in our study. The primary malignancies metastasizing to the liver in our study were identified as

- 28.84% from carcinoma colorectum
- 19.23% from carcinoma pancreas
- 13.4% from carcinoma stomach
- 7.6% each from carcinoma lung and breast
- 5.7% from unknown primary and carcinoma small intestine
- 3.8% from carcinoma gall bladder
- 1.9% each from carcinoma prostate, renal cell carcinoma, urinary bladder and endometrium.

The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing metastases in our study was 90.38%, 92.86% and 92% respectively which was in concordance to studies conducted by Jain et al [12] & Kumar et al [13].

Abscess

This was the second most common lesion encountered in our study. 41 cases (85.4%) were males who were more commonly affected, while females comprised 7 cases (14.5%). 64.4% of abscess were found in the right lobe of liver which was more commonly affected. This was also observed by Dewbury KC et al [14].

The hypoechoic echogenicity pattern with low-level internal echoes was more frequently observed, noted in 36 cases (75%). Additionally, 7 cases (14.5%) exhibited a hypoechoic pattern with posterior acoustic enhancement, while 5 (10.4%) cases

appeared anechoic. This aligns with the earlier research carried out by Thimmaiah et al. [15]. Most of the lesions showed well defined margins (87.23%) while only 6 cases showed ill-defined margins (12.7%).

However, we couldn't reliably differentiate between amoebic and pyogenic liver abscess only based on imaging in our study which require further clinical and laboratory data for confirmation. This concurs with previous studies by Ralls PW et al [16].

In conclusion, abscess appears as a well-defined hypoechoic lesion with posterior acoustic enhancement and internal echoes within. But, these findings were not diagnostic as other necrotic tumours or haematoma can also have similar appearance. This was also reported in a study conducted by Rubinson et al [17].

The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing abscess in our study was 95.74%, 98.06% and 97.33% respectively.

Hepatocellular Carcinoma

Among all the cases of HCC identified in our study, males accounted for 13 cases (86.6%), indicating they were the most frequently affected, whereas only 2 cases (13.3%) were observed in females. HCC was most seen in the age group of 61-70 years.

The prevalent echogenicity pattern observed was hyperechoic, noted in 6 cases with 4 lesions showing hypoechoic halo (40%). A mixed heterogeneous pattern was seen in 5 cases (33.3%), and hypoechoic pattern was present in 4 cases (26.6%). This was in alignment to the study conducted by Thimmaiah et al [15]. Hypoechoic pattern was most commonly seen in lesions smaller than 3cm. Calcification was not detected in any of the cases. All the cases showed increased vascularity on colour Doppler flow imaging.

The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing HCC in our study was 73.33%, 97.04% and 94.67% respectively.

Hydatid Cyst

Hydatid cyst constituted 9.3% of our cases. It was most commonly seen in males (85.71%) than in females (14.3%). All cysts exhibited well defined margins. The multilocular, anechoic pattern with daughter cysts was the most prevalent, observed in 5 cases (35.7%), followed by heterogeneous echogenicity, which occurred in 4 cases (28.5%). 3 cases (21.4%) displayed anechoic echogenicity with a floating membrane, while 3 cases (14.4%) were anechoic and unilocular. Additionally, wall calcification was noted in 3 cases. (21.4%)

Solitary cyst without daughter cyst is difficult to differentiate from a simple cyst unless calcification is present. Thus, the diagnosis of hydatid cyst is

certain only when daughter cysts are present. This was also reported by a study conducted by Bret et al [18].

The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing hydatid cyst in our study was 93.3%, 100% and 99.3% respectively.

Hemangioma

All the 5 cases were seen in male patients in our study. All the lesions had well-defined margins and appeared homogeneously hyperechoic with posterior acoustic enhancement. No internal vascularity was noted within any of the lesions.

The different atypical patterns of hemangioma make the differentiation quite difficult from liver metastases, especially in patients with a previous history of malignant tumour. This was also reported by Wu et al [19].

The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing hemangioma in our study was 100%, 99.32% and 99.33% respectively.

Hepatic Cyst

The typical appearance of simple cyst was seen in all cases which showed well-defined anechoic lesions with posterior acoustic enhancement.

The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing hepatic cyst in our study was 100%, 99.29% and 99.33% respectively which correlated with previous studies by Kumar et al, 2014 [13] & Jain et al, 2016 [12].

Biliary Cystadenoma

In our study, single case was documented. The lesion exhibited the characteristic appearance of well-defined margins and appeared as multilocular, anechoic lesion with internal septations and evident septal calcifications.

USG is more sensitive in detecting the septa in cystic lesions that help in diagnosis of biliary cystadenoma. This was also reported by Soares et al [20].

Complex cyst may be considered as a differential diagnosis on imaging. Diagnostic accuracy was 100% on USG as we had reported only one case.

Hepatoblastoma

In a 6year-old female, one case was documented and subsequently confirmed through histopathological examination. The lesion exhibited ill-defined margins and displayed a heterogeneous appearance, featuring internal vascularity and the presence of calcifications within it.

The diagnostic precision on ultrasound imaging was 100% since we reported only a single case. Our USG findings concur with previous studies describing a

large mass with a heterogeneous echogenicity and coarse calcification within as the most common finding in hepatoblastoma as reported by Dachman et al [21].

Cholangiocarcinoma

In our study, we had reported 2 cases of intrahepatic mass-forming cholangiocarcinoma with a diagnostic accuracy of 100%. Both the lesions had well defined margins. While one lesion appeared hypoechoic, other lesion showed heterogeneous echogenicity. Both the lesions showed focal intrahepatic biliary ductal dilatation with capsular retraction. One lesion also showed peripheral calcification.

Similar findings were also reported by Yong Eun Chung, MD, et al who reported that associated findings like capsular retraction, satellite nodules, vascular encasement without gross tumor thrombus

formation to be suggestive of cholangiocarcinoma [22].

Fibrolamellar Carcinoma

We had reported a single case of fibrolamellar carcinoma in our study with diagnostic accuracy of 100%. The lesion showed ill-defined margins and appeared hypoechoic with internal vascularity within the lesion. The lesion also showed presence of central scar with calcifications within.

Friedman AC et al [23] reported in their study that the major radiologic clue to the diagnosis of fibrolamellar carcinoma is the presence of central scar with calcification and they usually have nonspecific sonographic features, most commonly seen as well-defined masses of variable echogenicity on ultrasound [23]. Our findings were comparable with these studies.

Table 8: USG parameters to characterise benign and malignant focal liver lesions

IMAGING	TUMOR TYPE	
	BENIGN	MALIGNANT
USG	Uniformly anechoic with imperceptible/thin walls and septate	Hypoechoic halo
	Homogeneously hyperechoic	Bull's eye lesion
	Posterior acoustic enhancement	
COLOR DOPPLER	No internal vascularity	Presence of internal vascularity

In USG benign lesions typically showed imaging features like anechoic pattern of echogenicity with thin walls, posterior acoustic enhancement and homogeneously hyperechoic pattern. Malignant lesions showed imaging features of the presence of hypoechoic halo surrounding a hyperechoic lesion and Bull's eye pattern of lesion. Benign lesions showed no increased vascularity whereas presence of increased vascularity within the lesion were seen in malignant lesions. Similar observations were also made in previous studies by Jain et al [12].

The sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy of diagnosing benign and malignant focal liver lesions on USG in correlation with Triple phase CECT/ histopathology, in our study was 94.94%, 97.18%, 96% and 97.18%, 94.94%, 96% respectively.

The entire spectrum of focal liver lesions could not be studied as we had not encountered any other cases like focal nodular hyperplasia, hepatic adenoma, mesenchymal hamartoma, hepatic hemangioendothelioma, angiosarcoma and lymphoma in our study.

Limitations

- Small lesions may be challenging to detect or characterise accurately using USG alone, particularly if they are isoechoic compared to surrounding liver tissue.
- Diagnostic accuracy of USG in identifying certain lesions like Hepatoblastoma, Biliary cystadenoma, Fibrolamellar carcinoma and

Cholangiocarcinoma were 100% in our study as our study sample constitutes only one case each and hence a large sampled study may be advisable to corroborate our findings.

Conclusions

Triple phase CECT is done in atypical cases where ultrasound is not confirmatory and also before surgical intervention for precisely outlining the extent of the lesion. USG also remains a crucial component in the diagnostic pathway due to its ability to guide interventions such as biopsy or needle aspiration cytology and in post treatment follow-up. Hence, USG with colour Doppler should be used as a first line screening modality due to its high diagnostic accuracy in the evaluation of focal liver lesions along with additional advantages like its non-invasiveness, widespread availability, cost effectiveness and lack of radiation exposure.

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